

Non Boolean Logic and Non Newtonian Calculus Transformation of Internet of FAIR Data and Services (IFDS)

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Abstract—Internet of FAIR Data and Service (IFDS) came about as a transformation operation of internet infrastructure. By Category theory, it is possible to have further transformations in a systemic manner. Non Boolean Logic and Non Newtonian limit theory are here developed. Since the Non Newtonian limit theory gives rise to Non Newtonian Calculus, these along with Non Boolean Logic can be used to transform IFDS further. For Global Open Science Clouds (GOSC), the resulting transformation provides new tools and infrastructures for handling New types of Data sets as a result of the extension of FAIR principle.

Index Terms—IFDS, Category Theory, Non Boolean Logic, Non Newtonian Limit, Non Newtonian Calculus, Extended FAIR

1 INTRODUCTION

In Data Science, internet infrastructure has been transformed to provide Internet of FAIR Data and service (IFDS). IFDS has allowed machine reading and processing of data and has eliminated many of the problems of data interoperability, reusability, access and federation. However, data is continuously increasing in size and complexity. This becomes very obvious when dealing with interdisciplinary fields. To capture this complex nature of data, it is proposed to apply further transformations to IFDS by means of Category Theory. New transformers of IFDS are also introduced. These are the Non Boolean Logic and Non Newtonian calculus. Using these transformations a new extended IFDS based on extended FAIR principles is formed.

2 INTERNET OF FAIR DATA AND SERVICES (IFDS)

One of the core strategies of CODATA is the Internet of FAIR Data and Services (IFDS) [3]

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This is well illustrated by the hourglass, where data, tools and computation consist of the main components [2]. The original hourglass is shown below and it is transformed to IFDS hourglass by Transformation T1.

Fig. 1. The hourglass of the Internet

Transformation T1

Three hourglasses (I.e. the data hourglass, the tools hourglass and the compute hourglass) use merge-transformation T2 to give the data, tools and compute interconnection .

In summary , the key strategical aspects of CODATA IFDS is based on Transformation T1 and Merge-Transformation T2.

2.1 Catagory Theory of Hourglass Transformations

The Hourglass transformations T1 and T2 can be further generalized by category Theory [9].

If "A" denotes hourglass for internet and "B" denotes hourglass for IFDS, then by Category

Theory the transformation T1 can be shown as in the drawing below. $A \xrightarrow{T1} B$

We can now have new transformations on A giving A' and B giving B' which also gives Transformation T3 between A' and B'.

$$\begin{array}{ccc} A & \xrightarrow{T1} & B \\ \downarrow \beta & & \downarrow \gamma \\ A' & \xrightarrow{T3} & B' \end{array}$$

Here β and γ are general transformations.

This means the data hourglass (A1 to B1) ,the compute hourglass (A2 to B2) and the tools hourglass (A3 to B3) will have their own similar transformations as shown below:

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \text{Data hourglass} & A1 & \xrightarrow{T1} & B1 \\ & \downarrow \beta & & \downarrow \gamma \\ & A1' & \xrightarrow{T3} & B1' \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \text{Compute hourglass} & A2 & \xrightarrow{T1} & B2 \\ & \downarrow \beta & & \downarrow \gamma \\ & A2' & \xrightarrow{T3} & B2' \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \text{Tools hourglass} & A3 & \xrightarrow{T1} & B3 \\ & \downarrow \beta & & \downarrow \gamma \\ & A3' & \xrightarrow{T3} & B3' \end{array}$$

We can now use merge-transform T4 to merge these three transformed hourglasses B1', B2', and B3' to create a new Data, Compute, Tools based IFDS. This means any transformation in any one of the hourglass has to be accompanied with similar transformations in the other two hourglasses. Specially if the Compute hourglass is transformed then the Data hourglass and the Tools hourglass have to under go similar transformations.

As you can see the figure 2 shows the merge-Transformed T4 IFDS with Data based on B1', Compute based on B2' and Tools based on B3'. Previously , the merge-Transformed T2 IFDS was with Data based on B1, Compute based on B2 and Tools based on B3.

In summary , the key strategical aspects of CODATA IFDS is based on Transformation T1 and Merge-Transformation T2.

Fig. 2. Data-Tools-Compute: The merge-TransformedT4 IFDS has Data based on B1', Compute based on B2' and Tools based on B3' while The merge-TransformedT2 was based on IFDS with Data based on B1, Compute based on B2 and Tools based on B3. The question is, "Are the Data, Compute and Tools components transformed or not?"

3 THE DETAILS IN THE TRANSFORMATION OF THE COMPUTE HOURGLASS

Compute Hourglass in general has logic analysis and computation. The IFDS uses Boolean Logic and for computation, it uses Newtonian Calculus. Any transformation of the Compute Hourglass must therefore provide a Non Boolean Logic and a Non Newtonian Calculus based analysis.

3.1 Transforming Boolean Logic to Non Boolean Logic

How do you transform a Boolean Logic to Non Boolean Logic? The answer is given by the formulation of Boolean Logic by George Boole [5] the founder of Boolean Logic. See Appendix A for detailed derivation.

According to him in Figure 3, $x^2 = x$ defines Boolean Logic. The only two values satisfying "x" being "0" and "1". At the footnote of Figure 7 is seen the Taylor series derivation of the Boolean Logic.

To obtain the Non Boolean Logic we use the equation $x^n = x$. The solution to this equation is found by using Geometric Algebra numbers.

of Taylor's well-known theorem, viz.:

$$f(x) = f(0) + f'(0)x + f''(0)\frac{x^2}{1 \cdot 2} + f'''(0)\frac{x^3}{1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3}, \text{ \&c.}$$

$x(1-x) = 0$, whence we find $x^2 = x$, $x^3 = x$, &c., and

$$f(x) = f(0) + \left\{ f'(0) + \frac{f''(0)}{1 \cdot 2} + \frac{f'''(0)}{1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3} + \text{\&c.} \right\} x.$$

in (1), $x = 1$, we get

$$f(1) = f(0) + f'(0) + \frac{f''(0)}{1 \cdot 2} + \frac{f'''(0)}{1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3} + \text{\&c.}$$

Fig. 3. Boolean Logic Definition

Let

$$x = e^{i_1\omega_1t_1+i_2\omega_1t_1+i_3\omega_1t_1}$$

$$x^n = e^{i_1n\omega_1t_1+i_2n\omega_1t_1+i_3n\omega_1t_1}$$

The geometry of a spherical shape is produced by both x and x^n . The only difference is that of the speed of rotation. Confining the equation to that of shape only the equality of the equation gives identical shapes. This gives us a Non Boolean Logic where the x is defined as above.

If we extend the Geometric Algebra [8] number to i_n the equation will give us hyperspheres. If we restrict it to i_1 we just get a circle.

To illustrate the Non Boolean Logic, let us use two input Boolean Logic giving a possible four states 00, 01,10,11. Geometrically, these four states can be the four corners of a square which in turn represents four points on a circle. This means Geometrically the whole Boolean logical operation takes place on the circle.

If we now take up the sphere, we know that any unit sphere can be represented by two orthogonal unit circles. This means each of these circles represents a Boolean Logic. So the Non Boolean Logic for the sphere is represented by two orthogonal circles containing two orthogonal Boolean Logic, see Figure 5. So before one does a Boolean Logic one has to find out on which circle one is located. The transition from one circle to another is by rotation and this is now a new logical operation specific to the spherical geometry.

Hence the Non Boolean Logic for the spherical geometry contains two orthogonal Boolean Logic and one rotation operation.

Similar cases can now be developed for the hyper spheres. We have now established that for the Compute Hourglass the Logical analysis can be transformed from Boolean Logic to Non Boolean Logic.

3.2 Transformation from Newtonian Calculus to Non Newtonian Calculus

In the above section , one might argue that Non Boolean Logic can be any other Logic like fuzzy Logic, quantum logic, etc. We would argue that this statement is only partially true. When we look closely at the formulation of most logic we find out that there is a corresponding equation from which they are derived. For example Boolean Logic is derived from Taylor's series expansion of a function. Fuzzy logic is derived from the equation of probability and quantum logic is derived from Schrodinger's equation. So to understand transformation of one logic to another we need to understand what is happening at the equation level.

Normally mathematical equations are based on Newtonian Calculus which in turn is based upon Newtonian limit theory. So the real question is what is the Newtonian limit theory and can it be transformed into Non Newtonian limit theory? This question is really important because Newtonian Calculus and Newtonian Limit theory have remained unchanged since Issac Newton defined it in 1737 [6].

Here is a geometric definition of Newtonian Limit theory as given by Issac Newton in Figure 9:

Here is how the Newtonian limit definition proceeds in simplified form to a rotation in Figure 4: For details see Appendix B.

Quoting Isaac Newton: " And first , by way of preparation, it will be convenient to consider uniform and equable motions, as also such as are alike inequable. Let the right Line AB be described by the equable motion of a point, which is now at E, and will presently be at G. Also let the Line CD, parallel to the former, be described by he equable motion of a point, which is in H and K, at the same times as the former is in E and G. Then EG and HK be contemporaneous Lines, and therefore will be proportional to the Velocity of each moving

point respectively. Draw the indefinite Lines EH and GK, meeting at L; then because of like Triangles ELG and HLK, the Velocities of the points E and H, which were before as EG and HK, will be now as EL and HL. Let the describing points G and K be conceived to move back again, with the same Velocities, towards A and C, and before they approach to E and H, and draw gk, which will pass through L; then still their Velocities will be in the ratio of Eg and Hk, be those Lines ever so little, that is, in the ratio of EL and HL. Let the moving points g and k continue to move till they coincide with E and H; in which case the decreasing Lines Eg and Hk will pass through all possible magnitudes that are less and less, and will finally become vanishing Lines. For they must entirely vanish at the same moment, when the points g and k shall coincide with E and H. In all which states and circumstances they will still retain the ratio EL to HL, with which at last they will finally vanish. Let those points still continue to move after they have coincided with E and H, and let them be found again at the same time in y and x, at any distance beyond E and H. Still the velocities which are Ey and Hx, and may be esteemed negative, will be as EL and HL, whether those Lines Ey and Hx are of any finite magnitude, or are nascent Lines ; that is if Line yxL, by its angular motion , be just beginning to emerge and devaricate from EHL. And thus it will be when both these motions are equable motions, as also when they are alike inequable; in both which cases the common intersection of all the Lines EHL, GKL, gkL., etc. will be the fixed point L. "

To summarize, the rotation takes place at point L with the rotation axis outside of the page. The rotation creates a a rotation of the Line GKL rotating towards the Line EHL. Any ratio of GL to GK will go to gL to gk and finally to the limit ratio of EL to EH. At the limit the rotation angle ELG becomes zero.

In a Newtonian definition of Limit theory, the basic geometry is a rotation on a circle in a plain. For Non-Newtonian Limit definition, the geometry will be a sphere or hyper sphere. In the case of a sphere at least two orthogonal circles are required to describe the sphere as shown in Fig 5. Each circle , rotation-1

Data Hourglass or Tools Hourglass.

4 SOME APPLICATION AREAS OF THE TRANSFORMED IFDS

We believe the transformations mentioned above directly enhance IFDS by transforming it. This section gives a few examples on this:

4.1 Novel Data Set

FAIR is based on Ogden triangle or Semiotic triangle. This triangle was originally proposed by Ogden and Richards [7]. The formation of this triangle has some basic assumptions which are quoted here: "In The Theory of Definitions the following are considered:

1) Symbolization 2) Similarity 3) Spacial Relations 4) Temporal Relations 5) Causation: Physical 6) Causation: Psychological 7) Causation: Psycho-Physical 8) Being The object of A Mental State 9) Common Complex Relations 10) Legal Relations "

From the items listed above it is clear that a Boolean Logic and Newtonian Calculus are being assumed, see items 3),4) and 5). For a Non Boolean Logic and Non Newtonian Calculus , these assumptions are only using one circle with one rotation axis. This allows us to expand on FAIR principles by introducing another orthogonal circle on the sphere with a different orthogonal axis of rotation. The Non Boolean Logic and Non Newtonian calculus therefore make it possible to have two Ogden or Semiotic Triangles that are orthogonal to Each Other, thereby allowing us to have an expanded FAIR. Here the additional rules of Non Boolean Logic and Non Newtonian Calculus apply on the orthogonal data objects. If sets (Data Sets, Data Objects) obey Boolean Logic of intersection and Union, the orthogonal sets that are inputs to the Non Boolean Logic also obey their own rules.

4.2 New way of Looking at Inter Disciplinary fields

According to the above subsection, FAIR can be expanded based on orthogonal Ogden Semiotic Triangle. If we have two such orthogonal Triangles, we can assign one triangle for one

Fig. 6. Ogden Semiotic Triangle

disciplinary field and another orthogonal triangle for another disciplinary field. The geometric unification of the two triangles is that they are built on one sphere with two orthogonal circles containing each triangle. This approach can be used to unify different disciplinary fields and also use expanded FAIR tools to exploit the complex information from their respective data sets.

4.3 Computation as an approximation of novel computational machines

The current definition of computation is an approximation to analytical equations that do not have analytical solutions. These approximations do have a solution, hence we get to understand what the analytical problem poses. However, here we define Computation as an approximation of machines. Normally machines have their own architecture. For example Quantum machines have quantum architecture. These machines are difficult to build in their given architecture. However, by using computation we can approximate these architectures and get insight into these machines. In principle Non Boolean Logic and Non Boolean Calculus would need their own architectures. However, by computation , we approximate these machines and make use of them for novel applications.

5 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, IFDS can be transformed by using Non Boolean Logic and Non Newtonian Calculus. The key is the rotation aspect of the Newtonian Limit theory which can now be extended to Spherical and hyperspherical rotations in many dimensions. The Data hourglass, the Tools hourglass and the Compute hourglass can now be transformed using the Non Boolean Logic and Non Newtonian Calculus resulting in an extended IFDS and extended FAIR principles.

APPENDIX A PROOF OF THE GEORGE BOOLE'S BOOLEAN AND NON BOOLEAN LOGIC

In Figure 7, at the foot note of this page, it is shown how Taylor's series expansion of a function is used to derive Boolean and Non Boolean Logic.

APPENDIX B NEWTONS DERIVATION OF THE LIMIT THEORY

See Figure 8 and Figure 9

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Thus the form $f(x)$ would indifferently represent any of the following functions, viz., x , $1-x$, $\frac{1+x}{1-x}$, &c.; and $f(x,y)$ would equally represent any of the forms $x+y$, $x-2y$, $\frac{x+y}{x-2y}$, &c.

On the same principles of notation, if in any function $f(x)$ we change x into 1, the result will be expressed by the form $f(1)$; if in the same function we change x into 0, the result will be expressed by the form $f(0)$. Thus, if $f(x)$ represent the function $\frac{ax+b}{a-2x}$, $f(1)$ will represent $\frac{a+1}{a-2}$, and $f(0)$ will represent $\frac{b}{a}$.

9. *Definition*.—Any function $f(x)$, in which x is a logical symbol, or a symbol of quantity susceptible only of the values 0 and 1, is said to be developed, when it is reduced to the form $ax+b(1-x)$, a and b being so determined as to make the result equivalent to the function from which it was derived.

This definition assumes, that it is possible to represent any function $f(x)$ in the form supposed. The assumption is vindicated in the following Proposition.

PROPOSITION I.

10. *To develop any function $f(x)$ in which x is a logical symbol.*

By the principle which has been asserted in this chapter, it is lawful to treat x as a quantitative symbol, susceptible only of the values 0 and 1.

Assume then,

$$f(x) = ax + b(1-x),$$

and making $x = 1$, we have

$$f(1) = a.$$

Again, in the same equation making $x = 0$, we have

$$f(0) = b.$$

Hence the values of a and b are determined, and substituting them in the first equation, we have

$$f(x) = f(1)x + f(0)(1-x); \quad (1)$$

as the development sought.¹ The second member of the equation adequately represents the function $f(x)$, whatever the form of that function may be. For

¹To some it may be interesting to remark, that the development of $f(x)$ obtained in this chapter, strictly holds, in the logical system, the place of the expansion of $f(x)$ in ascending powers of x in the system of ordinary algebra. Thus it may be obtained by introducing into the expression of Taylor's well-known theorem, viz.:

$$f(x) = f(0) + f'(0)x + \frac{f''(0)}{1 \cdot 2}x^2 + \frac{f'''(0)}{1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3}x^3, \text{ \&c.} \quad (1)$$

the condition $x(1-x) = 0$, whence we find $x^2 = x$, $x^3 = x$, &c., and

$$f(x) = f(0) + \left\{ f'(0) + \frac{f''(0)}{1 \cdot 2} + \frac{f'''(0)}{1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3} + \text{\&c.} \right\} x. \quad (2)$$

But making in (1), $x = 1$, we get

$$f(1) = f(0) + f'(0) + \frac{f''(0)}{1 \cdot 2} + \frac{f'''(0)}{1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3} + \text{\&c.}$$

Fig. 7. Derivation of Boolean Logic and Non Boolean Logic

because $y = \frac{x^{m+1}}{m+1a} \times \frac{\dot{x}}{a} = \frac{\dot{x}x^{m+1}}{m+1a}$, taking the Fluents it will be
 $y = \frac{x^{m+2}}{m+1 \times m+2a}$. Again, if we make $n = -3$, 'tis $m+3a$:
 $x :: y : \dot{y}$, Or $y = \frac{xy}{m+3a} = \frac{x^{m+3}}{m+1 \times m+2 \times m+3a^{m+2}}$. And fo for
all other superior orders of Fluents.

And this may suffice in general, to shew the comparative nature and properties of these several orders of Fluxions and Fluents, and to teach the operations by which they are produced, or to find their respective fluxional Equations. As to the uses they may be apply'd to, when found, that will come more properly to be consider'd in another place.

SECT. III. *The Geometrical and Mechanical Elements of Fluxions.*

THE foregoing Principles of the Doctrine of Fluxions being chiefly abstracted and Analytical, I shall here endeavour, after a general manner, to shew something analogous to them in Geometry and Mechanicks; by which they may become, not only the object of the Understanding, and of the Imagination, (which will only prove their possible existence,) but even of Sense too, by making them actually to exist in a visible and sensible form. For it is now become necessary to exhibit them all manner of ways, in order to give a satisfactory proof, that they have indeed any real existence at all.

And first, by way of preparation, it will be convenient to consider uniform and equable motions, as also such as are alike inequable. Let the right Line AB be described by the equable motion of a point, which is now at E, and will presently be at G. Also let the Line CD, parallel to the former, be described by the equable motion of a point, which is in H and K, at the same times as the former is in E and G. Then will EG and HK be contemporaneous Lines, and therefore will be proportional to the

Fig. 8. Rotation in Newtonian Limit Theory Definition

locities at g and k , that is, at E and H; which contemporary Lines will be now as Ei and Hi . Let the points g and k continue their motion till they coincide with E and H, or let the Line GKI or gki continue its progressive and angular motion in this manner, till it coincides with EHL, and let L be the Node, or point of no divarication, as in the foregoing Lemma. Then will the last ratio of the vanishing Lines Eg and Hk, which is the ratio of the Velocities at E and H, be as EL and HL respectively.

Hence we have this Corollary. If the point E (in the foregoing figure,) be suppos'd to move from A towards B, with a Velocity any how accelerated, and at the same time the point H moves from C towards D with an equable Velocity, (or inequable, if you please;) those Velocities in E and H will be respectively as the Lines EL and HL, which point L is to be found, by supposing the contemporary Lines EG and HK continually to diminish, and finally to vanish. Or by supposing the moveable indefinite Line GKI to move with a progressive and angular motion, in such manner, as that EG and HK shall always be contemporary Lines, till at last GKI shall coincide with the Line EHL, at which time it will determine the Node L, or the point of no divarication. So that if the Lines AE and CH represent two Fluents, any how related, their Velocities of description at E and H, or their respective Fluxions, will be in the ratio of EL and HL.

And hence it will follow also, that the Locus of the moveable point or Node L, that is, of all the points of no divarication, will be some Curve-line Ll , to which the Lines EHL and GK/ will always be Tangents in L and l . And the nature of this Curve Ll may be determined by the given relation of the Fluents or Lines AE and CH; and *vice versa*. Or however the relation of its intercepted Tangents EL and HL may be determined in all cases; that is, the ratio of the Fluxions of the given Fluents.

For

Fig. 9. Rotation in Newtonian Limit Theory Definition contd.